

Constraint Effects in Compression Failure of Fiber Composites

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes recent developments in a model of the micro-mechanical aspects of compression failure in fiber composites. Although the compressive strength of fiber composites is often treated as a unique material property, there is ample evidence that the apparent compressive strength is sensitive to the details of the material form and the test or service condition. For example, the compression strain to failure in well-supported single fiber compression tests, tests of thin layers supported by a sandwich core in axially loaded columns, and bending tests all show higher values than in the more usual test results from axial compression tests. It is believed that these effects are systematic, and not just the result of test errors. A micro-mechanics model has been developed that correlates these data. The essential features of the model are that the fibers are treated as being initially wavy, that the fibers are stabilized under axial loading by shear stress in the matrix, and that ultimate failure occurs when the fiber-matrix interphase bond strength is exceeded. The calculations show that the effects of boundary conditions and laminate layups agrees well with experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Although the compressive strength of fiber composites is often treated as a unique material property, there is ample evidence in the literature to the contrary. In reality, it is seen that the apparent compressive strength is sensitive to the details of the material form and the test or service condition. For example, typical compression tests of AS4/epoxy laminates show a strain to failure in compression on the order of 1 to 1.3%. However AS4 fibers have also shown greater than 3% strain to failure in well-supported single fiber compression tests [1], 2% strain in tests of thin layers supported by a sandwich core in axially loaded columns [2], and greater than 1.4% in bending tests [3]. Further, it has been shown that the compressive failure strain can vary with the type of laminate being considered [4,5]. It is believed that these effects are systematic, and not just the result of test errors.

A micro-mechanics model has been developed that helps to explain the above data [5,6]. The essential features of the model are that the fibers are treated as being initially wavy, that the fibers are stabilized under axial loading by shear stress in the matrix, and that ultimate failure occurs when the fiber-matrix interphase bond strength is exceeded. This model has been used in previous work to show that the type of laminate can affect the predicted failure compressive strain. The present paper will give new model results that will help to explain experimental results in the literature.

Micro-mechanics models have played an important role in bringing out the salient features of compression failure in fiber composites as they are known to date. Extensive reviews of the literature have been given elsewhere [7] and will not be repeated here. Early work on modeling the failure process in compression by Rosen [8], Lanir and Fung [9], and Wang [10] pointed out the critical role of the matrix in supporting the fibers against micro-buckling. Further experimental work has supported key features of these models, such as the dependence of compressive strength on the shear modulus of the matrix [11], although complications such as the nonlinear behavior in

shear, (Wang [10], and Hahn and Williams, [12]), and initial fiber-matrix debonding (Lanir and Fung, [9], Barber and Triantafyllidis, [13], and Greszczuk, [14]) also influence the results. However it can safely be said that the available models are rudimentary and do not include all of the important features of compression failure, at least in sufficient detail.

A micro-mechanics model has been developed previously that includes a dependence on the through-the-thickness shear stresses. This model has been used in previous work to show that the type of laminate can affect the predicted failure compressive strain. The present paper will give new model results that will help to explain experimental results in the literature.

In the following the main ideas of the model will be briefly discussed. Calculations will then be given for compression failure in laboratory specimen that consists of an axially loaded column with an epoxy core, and comparisons will be made with experimental data. Additional calculations will be made for compression failure in beam bending, and again comparisons will be made with experimental results in the literature.

MODEL FOR COMPRESSION FAILURE

A micromechanics model for compressive failure of laminates has been presented previously by Swanson [5] and Swanson and Colvin [6] that will be utilized here. The model has a number of features that are similar to many others in the literature. As mentioned above, Rosen [8] has noted that the so-called shearing mode of fiber deformation appears to describe fiber microbuckling at realistic fiber volume fractions, and this will be utilized here. Additionally, a number of investigators such as Herrman, Mason, and Chan [15], Lanir and Fung [9], and Hahn and Williams [12] have included initial fiber waviness. The relations between fiber and matrix displacements and matrix shear stresses follows the treatment given by Hahn and Williams [12]. The essential feature of the present model is that it attempts to include through the thickness variations of fiber deformation and matrix shear stress.

As presented in [5,6], the model assumes microbuckling of fibers against the resistance of the matrix. The model addresses the case of initially wavy fibers (with an idealized sinusoidal waviness). Since the model assumes initially imperfect fibers, the "microbuckling" is actually lateral deformation and not bifurcation buckling. While the shear stiffness of the matrix resists the fiber lateral deformation, a limit to the fiber deformation is obtained by either the fiber tension or compression properties or the fiber-matrix shear strength. The basic ideas of the model will be illustrated in the following. The plies in the direction of the compressive load (termed the axial plies) will have the highest value of fiber direction compressive stress, and are therefore assumed to fail first. These critical axial plies are assumed to have an initial fiber waviness given by

$$v_0 = f_{10} \sin \lambda x \tag{1}$$

$$w_0 = f_{20} \sin \lambda x$$

where v is in plane and w is out-of-plane displacement. Upon loading the lateral deformation is taken as

$$v - v_0 = (f_1 - f_{10}) \sin \lambda x \ g(z) \tag{2}$$

$$w - w_0 = (f_2 - f_{20}) \sin \lambda x \ g(z)$$

where

$$g(z) = [1 - (1 - \alpha) (z/t)^2] \tag{3}$$

and α is an unknown parameter and t is the thickness of the axial ply group. The through-the-thickness variation (variation with the z coordinate) of the displacement occurs because of the additional plies in the laminate. That is, the adjacent plies of the laminate will tend to resist the lateral deformation, and continuity of displacement necessitates the through-the-thickness variation. The form shown for $g(z)$ is for the case where axial fibers are located adjacent to non-critical ply groups.

The deformation under load can then be solved for fiber lateral displacement by using a Rayleigh-Ritz procedure, with the parameters f_1 and f_2 governing the amplitude of the bending deformation of the fibers and the parameter α determining the through-the-thickness variation of the displacement. The task is to formulate the strain energy of the various components, and then to minimize the potential energy under applied axial compression displacements.

The strain energy terms are given as follows:

(1) Adjacent plies:

$$\gamma_{xy} = \left. \frac{\partial(v - v_0)}{\partial x} \right|_{z=t} = \alpha(f_1 - f_{10})\lambda \cos \lambda x \quad (4)$$

$$\kappa_x = \left. \frac{\partial^2(w - w_0)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{z=t} = -\alpha(f_2 - f_{20})\lambda^2 \sin \lambda x$$

$$U_1 = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^a \frac{1}{2} G_{xy} \gamma_{xy}^2 dz dy dx + \int_0^1 \frac{D_{xx}}{2} (\kappa_x)^2 dx \quad (5)$$

$$U_1 = \left\{ \alpha^2 \lambda^2 (f_1 - f_{10})^2 \frac{A_{66}}{4} \right\} + \left\{ \frac{D_{xx}}{4} (f_2 - f_{20})^2 \lambda^4 \alpha^2 \right\}$$

(2) In-plane shear in axial plies:

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial(v - v_0)}{\partial x} = (f_1 - f_{10})\lambda (\cos \lambda x) g(z) \quad (6)$$

$$U_2 = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^t \frac{1}{2} G_{12} \gamma_{xy}^2 dz dy dx = G_{12} t \lambda^2 (f_1 - f_{10})^2 h(\alpha) / 4 \quad (7)$$

where $h(\alpha) = [1 - 2(1 - \alpha) / 3 + (1 - \alpha)^2 / 5]$ (8)

(3) Through-the-thickness shear in axial plies:

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial(w - w_0)}{\partial x} = (f_2 - f_{20})\lambda (\cos \lambda x) g(z) \quad (9)$$

$$U_3 = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^t \frac{1}{2} G_{13} \gamma_{xz}^2 dz dy dx = G_{13} t \lambda^2 (f_2 - f_{20})^2 h(\alpha) / 4 \quad (10)$$

where $h(\alpha)$ is as given previously in Eqn (8).

(4) Out of plane shear in axial plies:

$$\gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial(v - v_0)}{\partial z} = -2(f_1 - f_{10})(1 - \alpha)(\sin \lambda x) z / t^2 \quad (11)$$

$$U_4 = \int_0^1 \int_0^t \int_0^t \frac{1}{2} G_{23} \gamma_{yz}^2 dz dy dx = G_{23} (1 - \alpha)^2 (f_1 - f_{10})^2 / (3t) \quad (12)$$

(5) Through-the-thickness tension in axial plies:

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{\partial(w - w_0)}{\partial z} = -2(f_2 - f_{20})(1 - \alpha)(\sin \lambda x) z / t^2 \quad (13)$$

$$U_5 = \int_0^1 \int_0^t \int_0^t \frac{1}{2} E_{33} \epsilon_z^2 dz dy dx = E_{33} (1 - \alpha)^2 (f_2 - f_{20})^2 / (3t) \quad (14)$$

(4) Axial compression of axial plies:

$$U_6 = \int_0^1 \int_0^t \int_0^t \frac{1}{2} E_{11} \epsilon_{11}^2 dz dy dx \quad (15)$$

$$\epsilon_{11} = \delta - \delta_b \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_b(z) &= \int_0^v \frac{v'}{2} dx - \int_0^{v_0} \frac{v_0'}{2} dx + \int_0^w \frac{w'}{2} dx - \int_0^{w_0} \frac{w_0'}{2} dx \\ &= \lambda^2 [(f_1 - f_{10})^2 g^2(z) + 2f_{10}(f_1 - f_{10})g(z)] / 4 + \lambda^2 [(f_2 - f_{20})^2 g^2(z) + 2f_{20}(f_2 - f_{20})g(z)] / 4 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where δ is the applied displacement per unit length in the axial direction. In the above, the elastic constants A_{66} and D_{xx} refer to the shearing and bending stiffnesses of the adjacent ply groups. The constants G_{12} , G_{13} , and G_{23} all refer to the shear moduli of the axial plies, and the modulus term E_{11} refers to the extension modulus of the axial plies.

The solution for either inplane or through-the-thickness lateral deformation can then be obtained by minimizing the potential energy with respect to f_1 and/or f_2 and α . The resulting equations give a complete solution to the fiber microbuckling (lateral displacement) problem. In practice, the solution for f for a given value of α can be found by solving a cubic equation. However the solution for α is more complicated and is most easily found numerically by standard root finding techniques. Once the values of f and α are determined from the minimization of the strain energy for a given value of applied displacement, the solution to the entire displacement field is complete. The in-plane and through the thickness shear strains can then be obtained by differentiating the displacement fields, and the shear stresses obtained by multiplying by the shear moduli.

The solution is a relationship between the amplitude of the displacement and the axial compressive force in the fiber. It is possible to place limits on the extent of lateral displacement by noting that the fiber lateral displacement may be interrupted by failure in one of several possible modes. Fibers that are inherently weak in compression such as aramid will fail by fibrillation, that is by coming apart laterally, at relatively low compressive applied strains (DeTeresa et al.[16]). Even fibers that do not fail by buckling must have some limiting strength, say determined by a slip condition in shear. Another mode of failure is fiber failure in bending, by exceeding either a tensile or compressive fiber strain. Finally, it is likely that failure of the matrix or the fiber/matrix bond will lead to loss of restraint of the fiber.

One can then consider the compressive strength of a laminate to be determined either by fiber failure, matrix failure, or failure of the fiber/matrix bond, and that fiber failure may be inherent in compression or augmented by fiber lateral displacement.

The strain in the fiber can be easily obtained from the model, consisting of a direct compression and a bending component that is related to either d^2v/dx^2 or d^2w/dx^2 . Thus when the fiber strain reaches either a tensile or compressive limit, the fiber is considered to have failed. The shear stress in the matrix can be obtained by multiplying the shear strain by the matrix shear modulus, as given by

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{12} &= G_{12} \gamma_{12} = G_{12}(f_1 - f_{10})\lambda \\ \tau_{13} &= G_{13} \gamma_{13} = G_{13}(f_2 - f_{20})\lambda\end{aligned}\tag{18}$$

Failure of the fiber/matrix bond is also based on the matrix shear stress as calculated by Eqn 18 above. The model at present is not of sufficient detail to discriminate between matrix failure and fiber/matrix bond failure. Thus by considering the proper limiting condition, on either fiber strain or matrix shear, a critical value of the applied compressive strain can be established.

APPLICATION TO AXIAL SANDWICH COLUMN TESTS

Tests have been reported by Whitney, Crasto, and Kim [2] on specimens that they referred to as "mini-sandwich beams", that consisted of two axially loaded face sheets bonded to a 3.18 mm thick core of epoxy resin. A compressive strain at failure of -2.1% was reported for face sheets of two plies of AS4/3501-6. This value is considerably higher than usually seen in other types of tests for this material.

A calculation was made for this test configuration, using the model described above. A value of 3.5° was used for the initial misalignment angle for all calculations. It was found that the predicted compressive failure strain was sensitive to the thickness of the fiber composite face sheets that are bonded to the epoxy core. An example is shown in Fig 1, where the predicted compressive failure strain is shown as a function of the number of plies of unidirectional 0° fibers in each face sheet. For face sheets thicker than about 6 plies, the predicted compressive strain value is essentially that predicted for a unidirectional fiber specimen alone, without the epoxy core. The predicted compressive failure strain increases with lower numbers of plies, with the predicted compressive failure strain increasing to 2.1% for 2 plies. This latter value agrees well with a value of 2.1% reported by Whitney, Crasto, and Kim for 2 ply face sheets. Clearly the thick epoxy core is serving to stabilize the fibers, thus increasing the apparent strain to failure in compression.

APPLICATION TO BEND TESTS

Bend tests have been used to determine compression failure values, which because they are typically lower than tensile values for high strength carbon fiber composites should be the limiting factor in determining bend strength. However in some cases this supposition is not supported by experimental evidence. A typical result of this latter situation is seen in the results obtained by Jackson [3], who noted that bend specimens of AS4 fiber actually failed in tension, rather than in compression.

The model discussed above can be directly used to predict compression failure in flexural tests, by assuming that the strain distribution is linear through the thickness. It can be seen from Eqn 11 that through-the-thickness shear stresses arise from the variation of fiber lateral displacement through the thickness. This shear stress tends to stabilize the fibers.

The predicted compression failure values in bend tests are shown in Fig 2 as a function of the specimen thickness. It can be seen that for thick specimens, on the order of 6 or 8 mm, the predicted compression failure strain is essentially that predicted for uniform axial compression loading. However, for thinner specimens the predicted compression failure strain increases until it exceeds the tensile failure strain for specimens thinner than 2 mm.

DISCUSSION

The main point of the present work is to demonstrate that a number of factors influence the compressive strain at failure in carbon/epoxy composites, and to suggest that at least some of these effects are systematic and can be understood by a mechanics analysis. Clearly, under many conditions the compressive failure properties depend on the boundary conditions of the test and cannot be considered an inherent material property. It has sometimes been considered that a "good" compression test is one that gives high failure values for a given material. For example, Berg and Adams [17] have shown that careful attention to experimental detail can result in higher failure values. The present results show, however, that apparent failure strengths are also influenced strongly by the conditions of the test, so that this criterion must be applied with caution. As an example, as discussed above sandwich column or sandwich beam compression tests typically show high compression failure properties [2,18]. The model results given here suggest that this is due to the support given to the axial fibers by the core. If the compressive failure values are to be used in design, then the tests used should be as representative as possible of the service conditions. If comparisons are to be made between material systems, then care must be used that the test conditions are the same.

Two major features of the present analysis were that compression tests run on axial sandwich columns with thin fiber composite face sheets are predicted to give high failure values, and that bend tests of thin specimens were also predicted to give high failure compression values. These features were supported by results in the literature. However it is clear that further experimental work and correlation with the model results would be interesting.

An interesting feature of the present results is that strong size effects were predicted in the form of compression strength being inversely related to thickness. It should be noted that these size effects are related to stress gradient effects, and are totally unrelated to statistical size effects, which were not considered here. This illustrates that interpretations of size effects must be made with caution.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Model results have been presented for compression failure of carbon fiber composites. The results help explain why certain compression tests, in particular sandwich specimens with thin fiber face layers as well as thin bend specimens, give high failure values. The model results indicate that the stress gradients in the specimens help to stabilize the critical axial fibers. The model results also exhibit strong scaling effects for thin specimens, that result from the stress gradient effects. The general features of the results are supported by data in the literature.

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Figure 1. Prediction of compressive failure strain in sandwich column of AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy. Results for 2 plies agrees with data of Whitney, Crasto, and Kim [2].

Figure 2. Prediction of compressive failure strain in bending of beams of unidirectional AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy. Results show that thin beams give higher apparent failure strain, and that the predicted failure mode of the beam shifts to tension failure for thin beams.